

PESQUISA DOS MODOS DE COMBUSTÃO DURANTE A QUEIMA EM GRELHA DE CARVÃO DE SHUBARKOL NA GRELHA DE COMBUSTÃO COM FORNALHA MANUAL DA CALDEIRA DE ÁGUA QUENTE KSVR-0.43**RESEARCH OF COMBUSTION MODES DURING LAYER-BURNING OF SHUBARKOL COAL ON THE FIRE GRATE WITH THE HAND FURNACE OF THE KSVR-0.43 HOT WATER BOILER****ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ РЕЖИМОВ ГОРЕНИЯ ПРИ СЛОЕВОМ СЖИГАНИИ ШУБАРКУЛЬСКОГО УГЛЯ НА КОЛОСНИКОВОЙ РЕШЕТКЕ С РУЧНОЙ ТОПКОЙ ВОДОГРЕЙНОГО КОТЛА КСВР-0.43**

ORUMBAYEV, Rakhimzhan K.¹; KIBARIN, Andrey A.^{1*}; BAKHTIYAR, Balzhan T.¹;
KASSIMOV, Arman S.¹; KOROBKOV, Maxim S.¹;

¹ Almaty University of Power Engineering and Telecommunications named after Gumarbek Daukeev, Institute of Heat Power Engineering and Control Systems, Department of Thermal Power Plants, 126/1 Baytursynuli Str., zip code 050013, Almaty – Republic of Kazakhstan

* *Corresponding author*
e-mail: a.kybaryn@aes.kz

Received 01 October 2020; received in revised form 28 October 2020; accepted 05 November 2020

RESUMO

Como mostram os números, a tendência de usar combustíveis sólidos no setor de energia do Cazaquistão permanecerá por um longo tempo. Com isto, a tendência mundial passa a ser o endurecimento dos requisitos ambientais, que impõem a tarefa de continuar a melhorar a eficiência da combustão do carvão, de forma a minimizar as emissões de substâncias nocivas e gases com efeito de estufa na atmosfera. O objetivo do artigo é realizar testes complexos de engenharia térmica da caldeira de água quente KSVr-0.43. Para isso, foram utilizados tais instrumentos de medição e controle como dispositivos secundários padrão da sala da caldeira, analisador de gases industrial Testo-350, módulo de controle (leitura) Testo-454 com sondas de temperatura e o tubo de Pitot, medidor de número de fuligem Testo-308, medidor de temperatura 2TPM1, medidor de fluxo líquido Vzlet-PRC portáteis e cronômetro com certificados válidos de verificação e calibração. A análise da composição dos gases, parâmetros técnicos da caldeira de água quente KSVr-0.43 realizada no modo de operação investigado com carvão de Shubarkol durante o teste de longa duração, mostrou que é possível operar caldeiras desta série em modos de baixa carga sem forçar o ar e combustível, permitindo reduzir as emissões de óxidos de NOx tóxicos e gases de efeito estufa CO₂ na atmosfera. Ao mesmo tempo, a combustão do carvão de Shubarkol sem forçar o ar é caracterizada por emissões significativas de monóxido de carbono CO. Os óxidos de nitrogênio NOx formados se decompõem em reações com CO para formar nitrogênio molecular e oxigênio.

Palavras-chave: *combustão, resíduo de coque na camada, etapas da combustão do carvão, emissões de substâncias nocivas.*

ABSTRACT

Experience shows that the trend towards using solid fuels in the energy sector of Kazakhstan will be implemented for a rather long time. At the same time, the global trend is currently tightening environmental requirements. They set the task to continue improving coal combustion efficiency and minimize emissions of harmful substances and greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. This article aims to conduct complex thermal engineering tests of the KCVr-0.43 hot water boiler. For this, the following measurement and control tools were used: the standard boiler room secondary devices, an industrial gas analyzer Testo-350, a control (reading) module Testo-454 with temperature probes and a Pitot tube, a soot number meter Testo-308, a temperature meter 2TPM1, a portable liquid flow meter Vzlet-PRC and a stopwatch. All they had valid verification and calibration certificates. An analysis of the gas composition and technical parameters of the KCVr-0.43 hot water boiler in the investigated operation mode with Shubarkul coal during a long-term test showed that it seems possible to operate boilers of this series under low load conditions without boosting air and fuel. They can reduce emissions of toxic

NO_x and greenhouse gases CO₂ into the atmosphere. In this case, burning Shubarkul coal without forcing through the air is characterized by significant carbon monoxide CO emissions. The formed nitrogen oxides NO_x decompose in reactions with CO with the formation of molecular nitrogen and oxygen.

Keywords: *burning, coke residue in the layer, coal-burning stages, emissions of harmful substances.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

Как показывают цифры, тенденция с использованием твердого топлива в энергетическом секторе Казахстана будет реализовываться еще достаточно долгое время. При этом мировым трендом в настоящее время является ужесточение требований по экологии, которые ставят задачу продолжать совершенствовать эффективность сжигания угля, максимально снижать выбросы вредных веществ и парниковых газов в атмосферу. Целью статьи является проведение комплексных теплотехнических испытаний водогрейного котла КСВр-0.43. Для этого были использованы такие средства измерения и контроля, как штатные вторичные приборы котельной, газоанализатор промышленный Testo-350, управляющий (считывающий) модуль Testo-454 с температурными зондами и трубкой Пито, измеритель сажевого числа Testo-308, измеритель температуры 2ТРМ1, расходомер жидкости портативный Взлет-ПРЦ и секундомер, имеющие действующие сертификаты поверки и калибровки. Выполненный анализ по составу газов, техническим параметрам водогрейного котла КСВр-0.43 в исследованном режиме работы на Шубаркульском угле при длительном испытании показал, что представляется возможным эксплуатировать котлы этой серии в режимах малых нагрузок без форсировки по воздуху и топливу, позволяющих снизить выбросы токсичных окислов NO_x и парниковых газов CO₂ в атмосферу. При этом сжигание каменного Шубаркульского угля без форсировки по воздуху характеризуются значительными выбросами окиси углерода СО, и образовавшиеся окислы азота NO_x разлагаются в реакциях с СО с образованием молекулярного азота и кислорода.

Ключевые слова: *сжигание, коксовый остаток в слое, стадии горения каменного угля, выбросы вредных веществ.*

1. INTRODUCTION:

1.1. Problem statement

The current state of affairs shows that the use of solid fuels in the energy sector of Kazakhstan will be implemented for a rather long time (Decree of the Government..., 2014). Simultaneously, the global trend is currently tightening environmental requirements, which set the task to continue to improve the efficiency of coal-burning and minimize emissions of harmful substances and greenhouse gases into the atmosphere (Liu *et al.*, 2017a; Chen *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, at the Department of Thermal Power Plants of the Non-profit joint-stock Company "Almaty University of Energy and Communications named after Gumarbek Daukeev", research is actively ongoing to develop new designs of hot water and steam boilers, mechanical furnace and burner devices with high efficiency, to reduce both specific fuel consumption and harmful emissions. For small and medium-sized coal-fired boiler houses, bed burning is typical (Kang and Ding, 2020; Maznoy *et al.*, 2020). According to estimates, for a layered combustion process, there are significant opportunities to intensify the combustion of solid fuels (Ermakov, 2005; Kamenetsky, 2010). In this case, the intensity of combustion on the surface of coal particles in the

flare process approaches its limit physically (Braconnier *et al.*, 2020). Layer burning of coal allows maximum retention and capture of solid coarse and fine fractions of slag and ash particles within the boiler on a grate (Ermakov, 2005; Kamenetskii, 2006; Kamenetskii, 2013a; Bao *et al.*, 2020).

Another aspect is that many boiler houses with low-power hot water boilers are located near residential buildings. Their chimneys rarely exceed 15-20 m and are low sources of toxic emissions and greenhouse gases. The total number of hot-water and heating domestic solid fuel boilers operating in the territory of Kazakhstan is tens of thousands (Fuel and energy..., 2018). Such sources of harmful emissions must have more stringent requirements for the content of harmful substances released into the atmosphere (Zhang *et al.*, 2017; Liu *et al.*, 2017b; Kornilova and Trubaev, 2018). However, coal prismatic and cylindrical coal-fired boilers with heat pipes widespread in Kazakhstan have an efficiency of not higher than 55-65%. Often, the water volume in a cylindrical boiler is several times greater than in a water tube boiler of the same capacity. The presence of a large volume of water in the boiler (especially in emergencies with frequent interruptions in the supply of energy and the cessation of water circulation with unauthorized

coal burning in a furnace with a large layer of coal) can trigger vaporization processes in the boiler and an accident (Volynkina and Pryanichnikov, 2002; Bochkarev *et al.*, 2011).

Conventional traditional water-tube boilers of a classical profile in active heat transfer used only up to 84% of the pipe surface (except for cylindrical) (Zhang *et al.*, 2018; Van Kenhove *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, a new series of solid fuel hot water tube boilers were developed with the minimum possible volume of water in the boiler and with the maximum (up to 96%) use of the pipe surface in active heat transfer (Alekseenko *et al.*, 2019). When creating a new hot water boiler (Orumbaev and Airich, 2007), the authors solved the problem of ensuring reliable operation at water pressures corresponding to the operation of hot water boilers, both according to the open hot water supply scheme (when the water pressure decreased to values close to the boiling temperature) and the closed-circuit (Rajić *et al.*, 2018). The connection order of the screens in the new boiler allows you to work effectively in operating conditions both in the optimal mode (with a nominal water flow rate) and to reduce the heat load by up to 20% with minimum water pressure and stable operation (Labidi *et al.*, 2017).

This article aims to conduct complex thermal engineering tests of the KCVr-0.43 hot water boiler (Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan).

1.2. Theoretical overview

Analysis of the results of tests performed in earlier works (Glazyrin *et al.*, 2010; Kamenetskii, 2013b) with small coal-fired boilers during layer-by-layer combustion showed a large unevenness in the content of CO₂ in the exhaust gases and the emission of nitrogen oxides NO_x. Measurements made at the time of the release and combustion of volatile components from coals with the content of a volatile component of V_{vol} = 35-37% showed that the concentration of NO_x in the exhaust gases behind the boiler with a fire grate and with manual maintenance is a maximum of 250-350 mg/m³, and the oxide carbon CO 15000-40000 mg/m³ (Kamenetskii, 2013c; Widziński *et al.*, 2019). In experiments with fuel boosting at a fire grate thermal stress of 300 kW/m², with coal burning in a layer, the maximum value of carbon monoxide emissions is 2.3%, at 454 kW/m² 3%, and at 715 kW/m², the maximum value of carbon monoxide is already 6.0%. The average values for a burning cycle of 10 minutes between casts, according to the test procedure, are 0.5%, 0.8%, and 1.3% with air excess factors of 1.32-1.44, respectively (Kamenetskii, 2006; Babenko *et al.*, 2017;

Jasinskas *et al.*, 2020).

Change in layer forcing (increase in air supply under the grates) in experiments (Kamenetskii, 2006; Kamenetskii, 2013b) showed that the nature of the gas composition curves does not change, but the length of successive burnout zones of coal is reduced. This is illustrated clearly in Figures 1a and 1b, which qualitatively and quantitatively illustrate the nature of Donetsk coal burning with a layer forced through the air from 875 m³/m²×h to 2430 m³/m²×h. This corresponds to the average airflow velocity w₀ = 0.23 m/s and w₀ = 0.68 m/s and the average thermal intensity of the furnace q_{furn} = 0.76×10⁶ kcal/m²×h and q_{furn} = 2.2×10⁶ kcal/m²×h, respectively. From the experimental data presented in (Ermakov, 2005; Kamenetskii, 2006; Kamenetskii, 2013a), an increase in air supply by 2.77 times increases the thermal stress of the layered furnace by 2.89 times. Simultaneously, the duration of CO formation is reduced by 2.66 times, and the absolute values of CO formation are reduced from 8% to 5%.

The experimental work by G.F. Knorre (1951) with a two- and three-row thin layer of spherical particles of solid fuel showed that after heating the layer and transition the layering process to the high-temperature coke burning mode, even such a thin layer is enough to consume all of the oxygen from the air passing upward through the thin layer of fuel (Barkan and Kornev, 2017; Król and Poskrobko, 2017; Nakamura *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, in the known and used in practice range of increasing airflow under a thin layer of burning coke (during forced combustion), chemical reactions in the high-temperature coke burning zone proceed at a much higher rate than oxygen supply, and the process proceeds in the diffusion region (Surawski *et al.*, 2020; Hampp and Lindstedt, 2020). At high temperatures developed in the layer, the reactions of reduction of CO₂ and H₂O on the heated surface of solid carbon begin to distill and displace the oxidation of solid carbon (Saha *et al.*, 2020).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In a boiler house preliminarily prepared for thermotechnical tests (Figure 2) with a KCVr-0.43 hot water solid fuel boiler with a fire grate area of 0.98 m² and a furnace volume of V_{furn} = 1.66 m³, the horizontal part of the flue behind the boiler was located in the boiler room. The boiler operates on such fuel as brown coal, hard coal. KSVR-0.43 (according to Figure 3) is structurally a solid-fuel hot-water boiler with a horizontal layout with a

layer furnace. The boiler consists of parallel pipes connected to collectors having partitions, external, ceiling and front screens, assembled in a furnace screen with the first and second collectors, a layer grid, herewith the water supply pipe is connected to the collector of the ceiling screen, and the front screen has a step collector connected through a rack to the bypass pipe connected to the first collector of the furnace screen, forming a loading opening for supplying solid fuel to the boiler. The ascending part of the flue behind the boiler is made with a three-fold increase in cross-section for collecting ash. In front of the chimney, a smoke exhaust was installed in parallel with a bypass to the main gas flue duct to ensure the reliable operation of the boiler and in natural draft mode (Nguyen and Sirignano, 2018). A chimney with a 325 mm diameter and a height of 12 m, preheated by the operation of the boiler in the nominal mode without a smoke exhauster, provided a vacuum of up to 100-150 Pa.

Complex thermotechnical tests were carried out, which consisted of a set of technical measures: instrumental gas analysis of the composition of exhaust gases in the furnace and in the boiler flue (by means of a portable industrial gas analyzer based on an electrochemical method for determining the concentrations of gas mixture components); instrument analysis of the heat transfer agent flow rate and assessment of the heat flow with standard and portable measuring devices (ultrasonic method using a portable ultrasonic flow meter with temperature sensors and using standard thermometers); technical analysis of the composition of coal fuel and furnace refuse (with sampling and analysis in a chemical laboratory using a calorimetric bomb). Complex thermotechnical tests of the KCVr-0.43 hot water boiler were carried out in an operating coal-fired boiler house and following the procedures (Kamenetskii, 2009; Kamenetskii, 2013c; Domestic heating..., 2016), with the authors repeatedly used in tests of other boiler units with tested measuring instruments. In particular, the following measurement and control tools were used: standard secondary equipment of the boiler room, industrial gas analyzer Testo-350, control (reading) module Testo-454 with temperature probes, and Pitot tube, soot number meter Testo-308, temperature meter 2TPM1, portable liquid flow meter Vzlet-PRC and stopwatch. All of them had valid verification and calibration certificates (Ruan *et al.*, 2020).

Technical characteristics of the presented batch of Shubarkul coal used in thermal engineering tests in an existing boiler house

(according to the data from the supplied fuel passport) were as follows: fuel carbon content of as-received basis $C_{\text{cont}} = (49.56 \div 51.81)\%$; total moisture of as-received basis $M_{\text{cont}} = (19.4 \div 19.7)\%$; ash content of as-received basis $A_{\text{cont}} = (13.6 \div 14.19)\%$; $V_{\text{furn}} = 44\%$; net calorific value of fuel $Q_{\text{ncv}} = (18.43 \div 23.11)$ MJ/kg or (4409.8 ÷ 5530) kcal/kg; $N = (0.45 \div 0.51)\%$; fuel sulfur content of as-received basis $S_{\text{cont}} = 0.42\%$.

The first series of above mentioned measurements were carried out on 30.01.2020 in two modes. In the first mode – during the period after casting a portion of Shubarkul coal in the burning layer and when a stable combustion mode was reached, at a boiler heat power $N_{\text{bhp}} = 230$ kW and a thermal stress of the combustion mirror (firebed surface heat release rate) $q_{\text{fbs}} = 309.3$ kW/m². In the second mode – during the period after the complete separation and burning out of volatile components of Shubarkul coal with stable combustion of coke. The heat power N_{bhp} of the KCVr-0.43 boiler was 136 kW, with the thermal stress of the combustion mirror q_{fbs} was 204 kW/m².

The second series of heat engineering tests were carried out on 02.20.2020 on the same KCVr-0.43 boiler without cleaning the convective heating surfaces. The thermal performance of the boiler in the first mode with the start of loading a new portion of coal reached $N = 248$ kW with a thermal stress $q_{\text{fbsl}} = 328$ kW/m², and in the second mode, after reaching a stable coke burning mode, the thermal performance was $N = 226$ kW with thermal stress of the combustion mirror in layer $q_{\text{fbs}} = 283$ kW/m². The conditions for the release of the heat-transfer agent as far as possible the operation of the existing boiler room remained the same. According to standard devices, the water temperature at the boiler inlet is $t_1 = 35\text{--}39^\circ\text{C}$, the water temperature at the boiler outlet was in the first experiment $t_1 = 50\text{--}54^\circ\text{C}$ and $\Delta t = 15^\circ\text{C}$, the average constant water flow through the boiler $G = 2.17$ kg/s.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The results of the heat engineering tests (Table 1) in the first mode and in the second mode on coal from Shubarkul coalfield on a boiler with a manual layer grate made it possible to estimate emissions by the content of O₂, CO, SO₂, NO, NO₂, NO_x, CO₂ in real operating conditions. Table 1 presents the measurement results for the periods 30.01.2020 and 02.20.2020. Each row displays the average values of the quantities in each experiment, divided by time. It should be

noted that the oxygen O_2 content is somewhat overestimated. Suction cups partially explain this through the loading door since it had to be ajar during measurements directly above the burning coal layer.

In the first part, the average values of the results of gas composition measurements in the furnace, at the height of 250-350 mm above the layer, and the boiler gas duct after 5-10 minutes from the moment of casting a portion of coal are given. For this regime, SO_2 and NO_2 , characteristic of the active phase of fuel combustion, are noted. In this case, the NO_x values reach their maximum values (up to 631.05 mg/m^3), and the CO content decreases (up to 1982.83 mg/m^3). The second part shows the average values of the results of the gas composition measurements during prolonged burning of the coke residue of coal with measurements at the height of 200-350 mm above a thin low-temperature layer of the grate. The second regime is characterized by the absence of SO_2 and NO_2 in the composition. The absence of NO_2 and the minimum values of NO_x (up to 48.07 mg/m^3) are explained by the active, reducing medium with a high content of CO (up to 32739.45 mg/m^3).

In the course of the experiment, the dependence of an increase in SO_2 , NO, NO_x , and exhaust gas temperature T_{eg} was observed as the distance from the front increased by 300 mm, 600 mm, and 1200 mm to the back wall of the furnace at the height of 200-210 mm above the layer of dying coke residue (uneven air intake with natural traction and the influence of cold air entering through front leaks). The total duration of the gas composition measurements continued in the active phase of combustion of about 40 minutes, and in the phase of the stabilized process of burning out of coke residue about 3-4 hours.

For the obtained data, calculation Tables 1-2 were compiled, and values were approximated with a confidence value of $R^2 = 0.63...0.91$. The lowest value was obtained for the curve of measurement values in the composition of O_2 , due to the technical impossibility of eliminating the suction of outside air into the furnace. Also, to preserve the properties of piecewise continuity, monotony, and limitation, values due to "misses" and a gross error in measurements were excluded. For data analysis, the most indicative time sections were taken from the data set of two test series 01/30/2020 and 02/20/2020. For each series, the average values and the obtained characteristic experimental data are presented in Table 2. Data analysis showed a clear separation of combustion modes. The first mode

characterizes the active phase of coal combustion with forced air supply. The beginning of the second mode occurs after the volatile components completely burn out, reduce the air supply by the blower fan and turn off the smoke exhaust, i.e., the transition to stable combustion of coke residue with a natural draft and without blowing.

Figure 4 shows the burn-up quality of Shubarkul coal with the smoke exhauster turned off and the airflow supplied by natural draft at a speed of up to 0.075 m/s under a thin layer of coal. The marked curves on the graph were obtained by approximation and smoothing by a polynomial (in this case, the approximation confidence value was $R^2 \geq 0.63$). Comparison with Figures 1a and 1b at an airflow velocity of $w_0 = 0.23 \text{ m/s}$ and $w_0 = 0.68 \text{ m/s}$ and an average thermal stress of the furnace $q_{furn} = 882 \text{ kW/m}^2$ and $q_{furn} = 2552 \text{ kW/m}^2$, respectively, shows that in Figure 4 with thermal stress of up to $q_{furn} = 193 \text{ kW/m}^2$, the graph of coal burnout in a thin layer is more extended in time relative to Figures 1a and 1b, while the harmful emissions of NO_x and CO_2 are significantly reduced. As can be seen from Table 2 and Figure 4, immediately after loading coal onto the grid and heating a fresh portion of solid fuel, the output of volatile components and its active burning increases the thermal stress of the combustion mirror and the thermal stress of the boiler furnace volume. Similarly, the level of NO_x emissions varies depending on the operating mode of the manual layered furnace and depending on the loading time of fresh coal (Figure 5).

An increase in the temperature of the torch over a thin layer of coal in the furnace affects the increase in water temperature at the outlet of the boiler on visually fixed secondary devices. During this period, the maximum NO_x emission is observed and reaches 10-15 minutes after casting up to 630 mg/m^3 , while the growth of CO_2 output begins and is about 7-8%, and the CO emission is about $1840\text{-}3680 \text{ mg/m}^3$ (Figure 6). After thirty minutes of burning coal in the layer after casting (the blower fan supply was reduced to a minimum, followed by switching off, and the smoke exhauster was turned off), NO_x emissions begin to decrease by more than a quarter from the maximum to $400\text{-}300 \text{ mg/m}^3$, the percentage of CO_2 is reduced to 4%, CO content increases by order of magnitude to 5000 mg/m^3 . In the next twenty minutes after stabilizing the coke combustion processes without forced air supply and in natural draft mode, the oxides NO_x and CO_2 continue to decrease, the SO_2 content in the gases decreases to zero the percentage of CO rapidly increases.

An hour and a half after loading, the maximum burning of volatile components and the beginning of stable combustion of coke of Shubarkul coal with a continuing natural decrease in the layer thickness in the natural draft mode, NO_x emissions decrease to 232 mg/m^3 , CO_2 content to 2.1%, CO content increases to the level of 23000 mg/m^3 . Further, the combustion process completely switches to the second mode (burning a thin coke layer). Stable indicators note this after 90 minutes of the experiment and 7-8 hours after casting coal. In this mode, the minimum values of $\text{NO}_x = 48.07 \text{ mg/m}^3$ are noted, while the values of the carbon monoxide CO content in the gases are maintained at the level of $25000\text{-}27000 \text{ mg/m}^3$. The intense onset of the burning of volatile components does not immediately warm up the entire fresh portion of coal above the layer after it is loaded. However, this ensures a high-temperature level in the furnace volume (Figure 7).

The staged combustion (characteristic of the works by Knorre (1951)) was obtained (Figure 1). However, this test process took significantly less time (Figure 8) due to several factors. First of all, forcing combustion through the air with a maximum flow of the blower fan ensured a powerful uniform flow with high speed. This intensified the process of active heating and combustion of fuel as much as possible, with the maximum yield of volatile components. Secondly, the process took the shortest possible time due to the layer thinness and the lack of fuel boost (the experiment was conducted for one portion of coal).

According to the data presented, it is clear that the oxygen zone is quite short, and the reduction reaction with the repeated formation of CO ($\text{CO}_2 + \text{C} = 2\text{CO}$) occurs quickly and stretches over a long period, stabilizing after 90 minutes of the experiment. In the active stage of combustion, the reaction oxygen content above the layer is already insufficient due to its consumption in the lower coke layer. Therefore, the nitrogen of the "late" volatile components during coke combustion does not have time to react due to the carbon surface reduction reaction. Therefore, short-term maximum emissions of nitrogen oxides from 555 mg/m^3 to 760 mg/m^3 after casting a fresh portion of the fuel remain at the level of (limiting) average values of nitrogen oxide emissions with the flare method of burning coals. However, after completing the active phase of combustion and the maximum yield of volatile components upon completion of forcing, the coke combustion process stabilizes but is characterized by unevenness in the layer area. Due to the impossibility of a uniform air supply, separate

active combustion zones arise under the layer, where there is enough air for the process, and "smoldering" zones in places where there is either insufficient air or the temperature is already shifted from the optimal reaction zone.

In (Kamenetskii, 2006; Babenko *et al.*, 2017) studies of the formation of nitrogen oxides when burning coal in briquettes, nitrogen oxide emissions are reduced by six times. In this work, according to the experimental results shown in Tables 1 and 2 and in Figure 5, values of NO_x emissions of the order of $150\text{-}48 \text{ mg/m}^3$ are achieved, and in the active phase after complete burn-up, volatile components emissions were of the order of 300 mg/m^3 . However, the obtained coke combustion regime without blowing and at a natural draft should be further optimized. So, with natural traction and without forcing through the air, the unevenness of the process increases over time. After a long period (7-8 hours) without casting a new portion of coal and forcing combustion, the furnace cools down, the intensity of combustion reactions decreases, and insufficient burning increases. Therefore, the process in this stage should be further optimized. This question is the goal of further studies of coal combustion regime in the bed in boilers with a manual furnace. In the future, it is planned to carry out new heat engineering tests to clarify and confirm the following conclusions:

1. Reducing the supply of blow air to a minimum under the fire grate with a thin layer of coal, and the results of experiments should show that the nature of the curves O_2 , CO, CH_4 , CO_2 , and NO_x does not change qualitatively. However, at the same time, their duration increases significantly, along with the burnout zone of the coke residue of Shubarkul coal.

2. When burning Shubarkul coal in layered furnaces with manual maintenance, keep a small thickness of the layer recommended for working with long-flame coals of not more than 100 mm and optimize the forcing process by air.

3. To eliminate the dip and entrainment of coal fractions less than $8\text{-}10 \text{ mm}$, the coal fines should be sieved since this size corresponds to that of the groove on all grates (conventional in the practice of burning in the bed) in furnaces with manual maintenance.

4. CONCLUSIONS:

The results obtained in the form of practical data on the operation modes of a hot water boiler allowed authors to achieve the research goal and

show the constructive need for organizing a stable combustion process with air supply (primary and secondary) by forcing the air supply or changing the design of the grate (in tests in a hot-water boiler, the cross-section of the grate was 20% of the total surface area of the grate). According to the data obtained, the possibility of implementation and separation into two stages of the combustion process (to efficiently burn solid fuel in a thin layer on a fixed fire grate) has been experimentally shown, and the operation of a hot water boiler with manual maintenance has been confirmed by the example of long-term burning of Shubarkul coal. The obtained work experience makes it possible to conditionally divide the first stage of coal heating, emission, and active combustion of volatile components with a further variation in the supply of secondary air to scarce combustion zones by the oxidizing agent.

An analysis of the gas composition and technical parameters of the KCVr-0.43 boiler in the investigated operation mode at Shubarkul coal during a long-term test showed that it seems possible to operate the boilers of this series under low load conditions without forcing through air and fuel. This can reduce emissions of toxic NO_x and greenhouse gases CO₂ into the atmosphere. Moreover, burning of Shubarkul coal without forcing through the air is characterized by significant emissions of carbon monoxide CO, and the formed nitrogen oxides NO_x decompose in reactions with CO with the formation of molecular nitrogen and oxygen.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS:

This research is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Grant No. AP05133388).

6. REFERENCES:

- Alekseenko, S. V., Kuznetsov, V. A., Maltsev, L. I., Dekterev, A. A., and Chernetskii, M. Y. (2019). Analysis of combustion of coal-water fuel in low-power hot-water boiler via numerical modeling and experiments. *Journal of Engineering Thermophysics*, 28(2), 177-189.
- Babenko, G. S., Zakharov, G. A., Sopova, V., and Tsygankova, K. V. (2017). Grate firing of low-grade coal having high moisture content in mechanised furnaces of low power hot-water boilers. *FEFU: School of Engineering Bulletin*, 4(33), 44-55. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1119159.
- Bao, J., Wang, D., Liu, F., Qu, Z., and Xu, H. (2020). Transient evaporation simulation of the forced circulation hot water boiler. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 721(1), article number 012068.
- Barkan, M. S., and Kornev, A. V. (2017). Prospects for the use of associated gas of oil development as energy product. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 7(2), 374-383.
- Bochkarev, V. A., Frolov, A. G., and Morozov, K. A. (2011). Improving the burning efficiency of azeisky in the boiler KB-TCB-20. *Bulletin of National Research Irkutsk State Technical University*, 8(56), 186-192.
- Braconnier, A., Gallier, S., Halter, F., and Chauveau, Ch. (2020). Aluminum combustion in CO₂-CO-N₂ mixtures. *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute*. Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1540748920300547>.
- Chen, L., Wang, W., Kong, Y., Yang, L., and Du, X. (2020). Hot air extraction to improve aerodynamic and heat transfer performances of natural draft dry cooling system. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 163, article number 120476.
- Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 724 "On approval of the Concept of development of the fuel and energy complex of the Republic of Kazakhstan until 2030". (2014). Retrieved from: <http://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/P1400000724#z45>.
- Domestic heating boilers fired by solid fuel nominal heat output up to 50 kW. Requirements and test methods. (2016). Retrieved from: <http://docs.cntd.ru/document/1200121803>.
- Ermakov, M. V. (2005). *Justification of priority areas for improving heat sources of small capacity with layered burning of brown coal*: thesis of the candidate of technical sciences. Irkutsk, Russian Federation: Institute of Energy Systems named after L.A. Melentyev SB RAS.
- Fuel and energy consumption in households in the Republic of Kazakhstan. (2018). Retrieved from: <https://stat.gov.kz/>.
- Glazyrin, V. A., Nenishev, A. S., and Orumbaev, R. K. (2010). Comparative

- analysis of coal burning in boilers of a new modification. *News of higher educational institutions of the Black Earth Region. Metallurgy*, 1(19), 67-71.
13. Hampp, F., and Lindstedt, R. P. (2020). Quantification of fuel chemistry effects on burning modes in turbulent premixed flames. *Combustion and Flame*, 218, 134-149.
 14. Jasinskas, A., Domeika, R., Jotautiene, E., Masek, J., and Streikus, D. (2020). Investigation of reed and bulrush preparation and usage for energy purposes and determination of biofuel properties and harmful substance emissions. *Engineering for Rural Development*, 19, 1953-1958.
 15. Kamenetskii, B. Ya. (2006). Optimization of the air regime of stoker furnaces. *Thermal Engineering*, 53, 473-475. DOI: 10.1134/S0040601506060140.
 16. Kamenetskii, B. Ya. (2009). Stages through which polyfractional fuel burns in a bed. *Thermal Engineering*, 56, 469-472. DOI: 10.1134/S0040601509060044.
 17. Kamenetskii, B. Ya. (2013a). Burning rate of solid fuel in the layer. *Thermal Processes in Engineering*, 5(8), 339-342.
 18. Kamenetskii, B. Ya. (2013b). Engineering calculation of heat transfer in layer furnaces. *Thermal Processes in Engineering*, 5(2), 76-79.
 19. Kamenetskii, B. Ya. (2013c). Radiation heat transfer in layer furnaces. *Industrial Energy*, 10, 31-34.
 20. Kamenetsky, B. Ya. (2010). Features of heat transfer in layered furnaces. *Industrial Heat Power Engineering*, 7, 14-18.
 21. Kang, Zh., and Ding, X. (2020). Numerical analysis on combustion process and sodium transformation behavior in a 660 MW supercritical face-fired boiler purely burning high sodium content Zhundong coal. *Journal of the Energy Institute*, 93(2), 450-562.
 22. Knorre, G. F. (1951) *Furnace processes*. Moscow; Leningrad, Russian Federation: State Energy Publishing House.
 23. Kornilova, N. V., and Trubaev, P. A. (2018). Analysis of MSW combustion temperature in a hot water boiler with the low-capacity. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1066(1), article number 012003.
 24. Król, D., and Poskrobko, S. (2017). Combusting fuel formed from waste. reduction in emission of chromium, nickel and lead. *Environment Protection Engineering*, 43(1), 101-112.
 25. Labidi, M., Eynard, J., Faugeroux, O., and Grieu, S. (2017). A new strategy based on power demand forecasting to the management of multi-energy district boilers equipped with hot water tanks. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, 113, 1366-1380.
 26. Liu, X., Yang, D., Lu, J., Guan, J., and Qi, G. (2017a). Combustion characteristics and design of hot water boiler. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 59(1), article number 012069.
 27. Liu, Z., Li, N., Zhou, Q., and Liu, T. (2017b). Study on the effects of external stress on hot corrosion behavior of steel T91 in the oxidizing atmosphere containing SO₂. *American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Power Division (Publication) POWER*, 1, article number 130327.
 28. Maznoy, A., Pichugin, N., Yakovlev, I., Fursenko, R., and Petrov, D. (2020). Fuel interchangeability for lean premixed combustion in cylindrical radiant burner operated in the internal combustion mode. *Applied Thermal Engineering*, article number 115997. Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1359431120334797>.
 29. Nakamura, Yu., Yoshitome, H., Yamazaki, T., Matsuoka, T., and Gao, J. (2019). Combustion of activated carbon particles part 1: Experimental investigation of the two distinctive burning modes in a packed bed. *Energy Procedia*, 158, 2152-2157.
 30. Nguyen, T. M., and Sirignano, W. A. (2018). The impacts of three flamelet burning regimes in nonlinear combustion dynamics. *Combustion and Flame*, 195, article number 170-182.
 31. Orumbaev, R. K., and Airich, Yu. E. (2007). Patent for the invention of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 18797. Hot water boiler. publ. bull. No 9.
 32. Rajić, M. N., Banić, M. S., Živković, D. S., Tomić, M. M., and Mančić, M. V. (2018). Construction optimization of hot water fire-tube boiler using thermomechanical finite element analysis. *Thermal Science*, 22, S1511-S1523.
 33. Ruan, J. L., Domingo, P., and Ribert, G. (2020). Analysis of combustion modes in a

- cavity based scramjet. *Combustion and Flame*, 215, 238-251.
34. Saha, M., Gitto, G., and Dally, B. B. (2020). Burning characteristics of grape marc under mild combustion conditions. *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science*, 114, article number 110059.
 35. Surawski, N. C., Macdonald, L. M., Baldock, J. A., Sullivan, A. L., Roxburgh, S. H., and Polglase, P. J. (2020). Exploring how fire spread mode shapes the composition of pyrogenic carbon from burning forest litter fuels in a combustion wind tunnel. *Science of The Total Environment*, 698, article number 134306.
 36. Van Kenhove, E., De Backer, L., Janssens, A., and Laverge, J. (2019). Simulation of Legionella concentration in domestic hot water: comparison of pipe and boiler models. *Journal of Building Performance Simulation*, 12(5), 595-619.
 37. Volynkina, E. P., and Pryanichnikov, E. V. (2002). Reducing atmospheric emissions from coal-fired boiler houses with fuel-bed firing systems. *Thermal Engineering (English translation of Teploenergetika)*, 49, 122-130.
 38. Widziński, M., Chaja, P., Andersen, A. N., Jaroszevska, M., Bykuć, S., and Sawicki, J. (2019). Simulation of an alternative energy system for district heating company in the light of changes in regulations of the emission of harmful substances into the atmosphere. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy Planning and Management*, 24, 43-56.
 39. Zhang, L., Jiang, Y., Chen, W., Zhou, S., and Zhai, P. (2017). Experimental and numerical investigation for hot water boiler with inorganic heat pipes. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 114, 743-747.
 40. Zhang, P., Liu, S., He, C., Tao, H., Qing, C., Li, P., and Li, D. (2018). Experimental and numerical study of the characteristics of biomass suspension combustion in a hot-water boiler. *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy*, 10(3), article number 033103.

Table 1. The results of measurements of the gas composition in the furnace and gas collection chamber

Test No.	Measuring point	O ₂ , %	CO, mg/m ³	SO ₂ , mg/m ³	NO, mg/m ³	NO ₂ , mg/m ³	CO ₂ , %	NO _x , mg/m ³	CH ₄ , mg/m ³	T _{eg} , °C
In the 1st mode – active combustion (after 5-10 minutes from the moment of loading coal)										
1	10-20', in the furnace, above the layer, 30.01.2020	16.80	6833.9	14.45	203.65	29.16	4.01	340.51	642.51	200.03
2	20-30', in the furnace, above the layer, 30.01.2020	16.89	8386.3	41.60	255.23	2.22	3.90	392.60	557.92	207.52
3	30-40', in the furnace, above the layer, 30.01.2020	16.62	8702.1	74.84	263.60	0.08	4.15	403.26	539.89	208.69
4	5-15', in the flue, 20.02.2020	15.11	2217.71	571.99	412.45	0.0	6.05	631.05	897.24	277.93
5	15-30', in the flue, 20.02.2020	15.30	1982.83	431.59	366.41	0.0	5.53	560.55	764.16	365.06
6	30-40', in the flue, 20.02.2020	16.04	6837.94	159.53	346.91	0.0	4.73	530.70	1451.99	267.45
In the 2nd mode – afterburning (after 7-8 hours from the moment of the last coal loading)										
1	In the furnace, over a layer of 30 cm, 30.01.2020	19.60	32739.45	0.0	72.12	11.73	1.29	121.93	1497.26	60.33
2	In the furnace, over a layer of 30 cm, 30.01.2020	19.59	31691.24	0.0	79.69	9.68	1.22	131.59	781.36	91.58
3	In the furnace, over a layer of 30 cm, 30.01.2020	18.77	31015.96	0.0	58.30	12.06	1.95	101.26	1748.40	74.72
4	In the furnace, over a layer of 30 cm, 20.02.2020	18.97	28781.08	0.0	86.95	0.0	1.79	138.48	2080.18	85.85

Test No.	Measuring point	O ₂ , %	CO, mg/m ³	SO ₂ , mg/m ³	NO, mg/m ³	NO ₂ , mg/m ³	CO ₂ , %	NO _x , mg/m ³	CH ₄ , mg/m ³	T _{eg} , °C
5	In the furnace, over a layer of 30 cm, 20.02.2020	19.82	28128.35	0.0	30.27	0.0	1.05	48.07	4616.83	67.33
6	In the flue, 20.02.2020	19.37	28298.06	0.0	79.61	0.0	1.45	122.89	3995.82	76.09

Table 2. Experimental test data (average values) of the KCVr-0.43 hot water boiler and coal characteristics

Parameters of the boiler KCVr-0.43, coal characteristics	The 1st mode (from the moment of coal casting), 30.01.20	The 2nd mode (in the long coke burn out), 30.01.20	The 1st mode (from the moment of coal casting), 20.01.20	Exit to the 2nd mode (stabilization of the process), 20.02.20
Ash content on working weight A_{cont} , %	13.61	13.61	14.19	14.19
Humidity M_{cont} , %	19.48	19.48	19.73	19.73
Nitrogen content, %	0.41	0.41	0.51	0.51
Net calorific value of coal Q_{ncv} , kJ/kg	22743	22743	23154	23154
Boiler heat power B_{hp} , kW	230	136	248	226
Consumption of Shubarkul coal C_{fc} , kg/s	0.0133	0.0088	0.0139	0.012
Thermal stress of the combustion mirror q_{fbs} , kW/m ²	309.3	204.2	328	283
Thermal stress of the furnace volume q_{furn} , kW/m ³	182.2	120.5	193	167

Figure 1. The composition of the gases over a thin layer of coal on a grate with a layer forced through the air when burning Donetsk coal at an air flow rate: a) $w_o = 0.68$ m/s; b) $w_o = 0.23$ m/s

Source: Knorre (1951), Kamenetskii (2006).

Figure 2. Diagram of the elements of the measuring system for thermotechnical testing of the boiler KSVr-0.43 (O and R – direct and return pipes of the heat-transfer agent; Ms, Ts – standard manometers and thermometers installed on the direct and return lines of the heat-transfer agent, dP – measurement of vacuum in a furnace with a Pitot tube probe, G1 – measuring the gas composition in a furnace with a gas analyzer probe, T1 – measuring the thermocouple Pitot tube temperature in the furnace, T2 – measuring the air temperature in the hearth under the grate with a thermocouple, T3 – measuring the temperature of the exhaust gases in the gas collection part (duct) with a thermocouple, G2 – measuring the temperature of the flue gases in the gas collection part (gas duct) with a gas analyzer probe

Figure 3. Front and side view of the hot water solid fuel boiler KSVR-0.43

Figure 4. The composition of the gases over a thin coal layer on a grate with forced air over the layer and during natural draft at burning Shubarkul coal in a layer up to 70 mm at an airflow rate of $w_0 = 0.075 \text{ m/s}$ (with separation of the combustion regime time: 0-80 minutes – from the moment of coal loading; 430-520 minutes – during the stable process of coke burning out)

Figure 5. Approximate NO_x and SO_2 content measurement data for two combustion modes

Figure 6. Approximate CO and CO_2 content measurements data for two combustion modes

Figure 7. Approximate data of measurements of the temperature of gases in the furnace for two combustion modes

Figure 8. Measurement data of CO and CO₂ in the active stage of burning of Shubarkul coal with forced air